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Machine Learning to Augment Shared Knowledge in
Federated Privacy-Preserving Scenarios (MUSKETEER)

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**D4.3 Pre-processing, normalization, data
alignment and data value estimation
algorithms – Final version**

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Author(s): Ángel Navia-Vázquez (UC3M), Jesús Cid-Sueiro (UC3M),
Manuel Vázquez-López (UC3M)

Participant(s): Roberto Díaz (Tree Technology), Marcos Fernández (Tree
Technology), Jaime Medina (Tree Technology)

Reviewer(s): Susanna Bonura (ENG), Ambrish Rawat (IBM)

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Contact: angel.navia@uc3m.es

Website: www.MUSKETEER.eu

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Executive Summary

This deliverable (D4.3 "Pre-processing, normalization, data alignment and data value estimation: Final version") describes the functionalities included in the MUSKETEER Machine Learning Library (MMLL) with respect to preprocessing, normalization, data alignment and value estimation, as described in the DoA (task T4.2). This document represents an update to D4.2. Besides the code included in the MMLL library itself, D4.3 comprises a report with the description of the usage and operation of the above mentioned MMLL functionalities under different demo scenarios. Namely, fully integrated mechanisms in MMLL that operate on horizontally or vertically partitioned datasets are provided for¹:

- Input data definition verification
- Data conversion to numeric format
- Data pre-processing
- Data (global parameter) normalization
- Dimensionality reduction:
 - Principal Component Analysis
 - Feature Selection (greedy, sparse frequency)
 - Random projection (full, sparse)
- Deep Learning Image Preprocessing
- Natural Language Processing
- Record linkage
- Missing data imputation
- A priori² data alignment estimation

¹ Depending on the POM or vertical/horizontal partitioning, some functionalities may not be available in MMLL.

² The methods provided here for data alignment estimation and data value estimation are named as “a priori” because they operate during the pre-processing stage, i.e., before the interaction during the training phase takes place. Additional estimation methods associated with the training algorithms developed in the POMs will be provided.

- Data value estimation

After one or more of these techniques have been applied, any of the training methods available at MMLL can be applied to obtain a trained Machine Learning model.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AUC	Area Under (ROC) Curve
CA	Consortium Agreement
DAE	Data Alignment Estimation
DC	Data Connector
DF	Document Frequency
DL	Deep Learning
DVE	Data Value Estimation
FS	Feature Selection
GA	Grant Agreement
GDVE	Greedy “a posteriori” Data Value Estimation
LC	Logistic Classifier
LGFS	Linear Greedy Feature Selection
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MMLL	MUSKETEER Machine Learning Library
MN	Master Node
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NLTK	Natural Language Toolkit
ODVE	“On-line” Data Value Estimation
OS	Operating System
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PDVE	“A priori” Data Value Estimation
PERT	Program evaluation and review technique
POM	Privacy Operation Mode
PP	Privacy Preserving
PPML	Privacy Preserving Machine Learning (a.k.a. Privacy Preserving Data Mining)
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristics
RP	Random Projection
SDP	Secure Dot Product
SV	Statistics Vector
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
TA	Total Alignment
TF	Term Frequency
TFIDF	Term Frequency, Inverse Document Frequency
WN	Worker Node

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This deliverable provides a functional description of the MUSKETEER capabilities for data pre-processing, data normalization, data alignment estimation and data value estimation, as well as a detailed usage demonstration of the corresponding implemented methods in the MUSKETEER Machine Learning Library (MMLL). We provide methods operating under different confidentiality preserving conditions (Privacy Operation Modes, or POMs). In every one of the described methods, it is indicated which kind of information is exchanged among the aggregator (also named sometimes as Master) and participants (a.k.a. Workers) but, in all cases, the data confidentiality is preserved since raw data is never exchanged among participants.

1.2 Related Documents

The MUSKETEER Machine Learning Library (MMLL) v0.6 together with this report comprises Deliverable D4.3, (WP4, T4.2) and describes functionalities that provide a complementary set of tools to be used in conjunction with the training methods developed in WP4 (as described in D4.4 and D4.6). D4.3 will also provide valuable information to WP7 (Client side connector implementation and use case piloting), as indicated in the PERT diagram below, such that the data analysis/processing pipeline is enriched with this new set of tools. In general terms, it constitutes a tangible outcome such that any member of the consortium can carry out "hands on" experimentation with MMLL not only in model training but also in data pre-processing/analysis, and such interactions could provide relevant feedback among all participants to further improve the results on the use case scenarios.

Figure 1: MUSKETEER’s PERT diagram

1.3 Document Structure

This document is structured as follows:

- The current section (Introduction) presents the general aspects about this document, the associated software tools incorporated to MMLL and its relationship with other developments in the project.
- The section "MUSKETEER Machine Learning Library (MMLL) revisited" briefly describes the main objectives of MUSKETEER from a Machine Learning point of view, as well as the main MMLL components and communications mechanisms available. We explicitly revisit the two aggregation methods available in MUSKETEER: direct aggregation, and secure aggregation via round robin mechanism, which are the bases of many of the developed learning and processing methods. We also revisit the two main data partition scenarios: horizontal and vertical partitioning, and their implications from a Machine Learning point of view.
- The section "Preliminary steps before training an ML model" describes the potential list of operations on the data that can be carried out –if deemed necessary- before actually training a model. We discuss the following pre-processing steps: input/output data type verification, categorical/text/image conversion to numeric format, “ad hoc” pre-processing (logarithmic re-scaling, outlier clipping, image pre-processing), a priori data alignment estimation, data normalization, and

dimensionality reduction (Principal Component Analysis (PCA), feature selection, random projection).

- The section "Privacy preserving record linkage" covers a specific topic in the vertical partitioning setup, the need to establish a relationship among different features corresponding to the same training pattern that are stored at different locations. A derived problem from this one is missing data imputation, since after organizing all the available information from the different participants, it may happen that some features corresponding to some training patterns are missing.
- In Section 4: "Data value estimation", we explain the implemented methods to estimate the value corresponding to every contributed data chunk. We provide methods for "a priori" data value estimation, for online estimation and also a general procedure for a more accurate but complex "a posteriori" data value estimation. These methods will be valuable for the deployment of data economy scenarios, as described in WP6.
- The Section "Software installation instructions" describes how to download and install the MMLL library and the corresponding demos in a python3 environment for basic functionality testing. A more complete description of MUSKETEER usage for end users will be provided in the context of WP7, where the MUSKETEER client is used to deploy end user use case demos.
- The Section "Demos" indicates how to run specific demonstrations to illustrate any of the functionalities described in this report.
- Last but not least, the Conclusions and References sections bring the report to an end, providing a summary of what has been presented and also some additional information sources for the interested reader that wants to get more details about some of the used technologies and methods.

2 The MUSKETEER Machine Learning Library (MMLL) revisited

In D4.4 and D4.6 a full description and demonstration of some Machine Learning models already implemented in MMLL under the different POMs is provided. The new functionalities developed under Task 4.2 are covered here: pre-processing, normalization, data alignment estimation and data value estimation. We will briefly revisit the main MMLL concepts for a better understanding of the algorithms' operation.

The MUSKETEER platform aims at solving Machine Learning (ML) problems using data from different users while preserving the confidentiality of the data. Essentially, it aims at

deploying a distributed ML setup (Figure 2(b)) such that the model ultimately trained is equivalent to the one that would be obtained in the centralized setup (Figure 2(a)).

Figure 2: The centralized (a) vs. (privacy/confidentiality preserving) distributed scenario (b).

The centralized solution shown in Figure 2(a) would require that the data from different users is gathered in a common location, something that is not always possible due to privacy/confidentiality restrictions. On the other hand, the distributed privacy-preserving approach requires exchanging some information among the participating users such that some of them obtain the final ML model without ever receiving/seeing the raw data of the other users.

2.1 The Data Value estimation problem

Under this setup, several participants may want to cooperate to train a joint model, but the amount and the quality of the data provided by every one of them is not known beforehand. Actually, some of them could even be malicious, and try to inject low quality or directly "poisonous" data into the learning process. Obviously, all of them could declare that they are contributing with a large amount of high quality data, but that is something to be further assessed by the Master node controlling the learning process, since in a data economy, an economic reward must be assigned to every participant, according to their real contribution (Data Value). Therefore, the tasks of detecting the 'alignment of every participant data' with respect to the defined task is a very important preliminary step, since the inclusion of "bad" data in the learning process could largely bias the resulting model. A thorough analysis of these types of attacks and of potential strategies for defending against them will be carried out in the context of WP5 - Security and Trustworthiness of Federated Machine Learning

Algorithms, and the results produced therein will help in reducing the risk of incorporating data that may impair the learning process. Hence, the techniques provided in T4.2 for data alignment estimation can be seen as an “a priori” estimate such that the less aligned data contributions can be removed from the training procedure at an early stage. If the provided techniques do not provide a clear verdict about a given participant, those users that are dubious can be included in the training process, since the methods provided in WP5 will be able to detect and filter out their contribution during training time, if needed.

2.2 Data aggregation procedures

Most of the distributed training/pre-processing procedures need, at some point, to aggregate information from the workers. However, in some scenarios it can be assumed that the Master node knows the specific contribution from every worker whereas in others more confidentiality-restrictive situations, the Master node should only get access to the global aggregated amount. Secure Data Aggregation is a well-studied problem [Chan_2010], and a Secure Aggregation Protocol (SAP) is defined in [Bonawitz_2017] as *any procedure that provides a global parameter aggregation without revealing the particular contribution from every participant*. Many Privacy Preserving techniques can be used to achieve that objective. In MUSKETEER we have two communication mechanisms that allow us to implement two different kinds of aggregation procedures: direct aggregation and round-robin aggregation, the latter providing the Secure Aggregation Protocol.

2.2.1 Direct aggregation

This kind of aggregation relies on a star topology in the communications service, such that direct messages are sent from the Workers to the Master node, which receives the specific contribution from every Worker and builds the aggregated result. This is the simplest procedure but it reveals to the Master node the specific value contributed by every Worker. In Figure 3 below we illustrate this procedure using a simple task to obtain the total number of training patterns available among all Workers (numbers marked in a blue circle at every Worker). The Master node receives every contribution to obtain the final result (18).

Figure 3: Direct aggregation procedure using a star topology.

2.2.2 Round-robin aggregation

When the individual values cannot be revealed to the Master node or to other Workers, a round-robin protocol running on a ring topology provides an elegant and secure procedure. First of all, the Master node generates a random value to initiate the communication. This value (145 in this example) is sent to the first Worker, who adds its own value. The next Worker receives the updated value of 152, such that it cannot differentiate between the data from the previous Worker and the random value from the Master node. The procedure continues until the Master node receives the total accumulated value (163) and computes the final result by subtracting the initial random value (163-145 = 18). As a result, the Master node obtains the total accumulated value, but it receives no information of the specific contribution from every Worker.

Figure 4: Secure aggregation procedure based on a round-robin protocol using a ring topology.

Furthermore, if the scheme depicted in Figure 4 is deemed insecure because of the possibility of some partial results being revealed due to collusion in the communication service, an additional encryption layer could be added such that only the Master Node is able to decrypt the final aggregation result. This enhanced security scheme is depicted in Figure 5, where the numbers in double square brackets represent encrypted values.

Figure 5: Secure aggregation procedure based on a round-robin protocol using a ring topology and encrypted messages.

In this case, the Master is the only one that can decrypt the messages, and the aggregations are carried out in every participant taking advantage of the homomorphic properties of the cryptographic scheme. Hence, the computation is secure since neither the participants nor the communication service can learn anything about the final or partial results.

This being said, the above described procedures can be used to aggregate not only single values, but more complex structures, such as vectors or even models, such that aggregations of models, gradients, or even vocabularies can be computed under different confidentiality constraints.

2.3 Data partitioning schemes

We will briefly revisit here the two most common data partitioning scenarios, that depend on how the different participants contribute to a global collection of training data [Pajwani_2013]. The first, and possibly the most well-known, is horizontal data partitioning, in which every participant has access to a subset of complete input patterns (every one of them has all of the input features). On the other side, in the vertical partitioning scheme we assume that every participant only provides a subset of input features about a given training record. In Figure 6 we illustrate the two aforementioned partitioning options.

Figure 6: Horizontal vs. vertical data partitioning.

In what follows, we will discuss in more detail each one of these situations, and briefly comment on the implications they have in the operation of the algorithms under every POM.

2.3.1 Horizontal data partitioning

This is a common situation where every participant can get access to a full-featured measurement about a given process, and also has access to a target value for that training

pattern. Examples could be, for instance, labelled images or documents available at every participant, or measurements on a given industrial process which is the same for all participants. In this case, the participants need to agree on the number and the type of input features and target value for a given task. As will be discussed later, in the MUSKETEER context this preliminary data format agreement is attained after the task definition process and the sharing of input and target data descriptions. Take for instance this input data matrix example:

User ID	Height(cm)	Weight(Kg)	Age (years)	Income (k€)	Hobby	Heartbeat
1	176	54	36	23	Tennis	54
2	165	76	45	87	Biking	67
3	198	86	87	56	Yoga	88
4	154	70	24	99	Walking	45
5	167	46	78	12	Reading	91

Figure 7: Sample data matrix.

Under a horizontal partitioning scheme, this data could be located at two different participants, each one having a portion of the table:

Data at participant No. 1						Data at participant No. 2					
Height	Weight	Age	Income	Hobby	Heartbeat	Height	Weight	Age	Income	Hobby	Heartbeat
176	54	36	23	Tennis	54	198	86	87	56	Yoga	88
165	76	45	87	Biking	67	154	70	24	99	Walking	45
						167	46	78	12	Reading	91

Figure 8: Sample horizontally data partitioning.

Both of them provide sub-tables with the same feature structure, since they both know the order and type of the input features. Note that once the input features are agreed among the participants, there is no need to maintain a user ID record, which is usually good news, since it facilitates data anonymization. This approach leads to full data matrices (no missing data), unless some input features are already missing in the original data partitions.

2.3.2 Vertical data partitioning

In this situation every participant usually provides, for a given input pattern, different input features to the learning process. A classic example is that of medical applications, where every patient can be uniquely identified (for instance, by means of a Social Security number, Passport ID or full name). In this scenario, one patient may have been treated or examined at different hospitals and every hospital may have a different (hopefully complementary) set

of features for that patient. Continuing with the example in the previous section, a vertical partitioning for data matrix in Figure 7 could be:

Data at participant No. 1				Data at participant No. 2			
User ID	Height (cm)	Weight (Kg)	Age (years)	User ID	Income (k€)	Hobby	Heartbeat
1	176	54	36	1	23	Tennis	54
2	165	76	45	2	87	Biking	67
3	198	86	87	3	56	Yoga	88
4	154	70	24	4	99	Walking	45
5	167	46	78	5	12	Reading	91

Figure 9: Sample vertical data partitioning with complete records.

In this case it is necessary to maintain a unique global ID such that different input features can be associated with their corresponding owner. This problem is known as the *record linkage problem* [Winkler_1999] [Adil_2017] and, in a general setting, it can be very complex, especially when it is not so straightforward to obtain a unique global identifier. We will provide solutions for deterministic record linkage, where a unique ID is assumed to be available. The partition depicted in Figure 9 assumes that all IDs are present at all participants and hence, a full data matrix is obtained when we join the partitions.

Unfortunately this is not the most common case, since information from a given user may not be available at a given participant. This incomplete case has been illustrated in Table 10 below.

Data at participant No. 1				Data at participant No. 2			
User ID	Height (cm)	Weight (Kg)	Age(years)	User ID	Income (k€)	Hobby	Heartbeat
1	176	54	36	2	87	Biking	67
2	165	76	45	3	56	Yoga	88
3	198	86	87	6	65	Sleeping	77
4	154	70	24	7	78	Gaming	56
5	167	46	78				

Figure 10: Sample vertical data partitioning with incomplete records.

In this second situation, a data matrix with missing values is obtained after the record linkage, as shown in the next Figure.

User ID	Height(cm)	Weight (Kg)	Age (years)	Income (k€)	Hobby	Heartbeat
1	176	54	36	-	-	-
2	165	76	45	87	Biking	67
3	198	86	87	56	Yoga	88
4	154	70	24	-	-	-
5	167	46	78	-	-	-
6	-	-	-	65	Sleeping	77
7	-	-	-	78	Gaming	56

Figure 11: Joint data matrix after record linkage in an incomplete setting.

Under this scenario there are two possibilities: we can either apply any data imputation technique, to fill in the missing fields, or we can filter out the incomplete records and retain only the full input patterns for the training phase. Both approaches have been implemented in MUSKETEER, as will be explained later.

In summary, before starting a training procedure it is advisable to carry out a series of pre-processing steps to maximize the success of the model adjustment process. In the next section we will describe the sequence of those steps and how they can be applied in the context of the MMLL.

3 Preliminary steps before training an ML model

In this section we will describe the data operations to be carried out before running a given training process under any POM. It is not mandatory to always apply all of the described methods, they are just available at MMLL and the Data Scientist who is building a Data Processing pipeline decides which ones to apply.

In each case, we will describe the expected input and output and the implemented operation. In summary, these are the recommended steps to follow before training a model:

- **Input/output data type verification:** the data provided by the participants (workers) can be of any type and format. Before joining a given training task, any participant is aware of the type of data required to contribute to that task, and should only provide compatible data. However, it is always recommended to check that the data provided by the workers has the correct format according to what has been agreed upon. This is a horizontally partitioning-specific operation, since in vertical partitioning every participant will be providing their own input features.
- **Data conversion to numeric format:** some kind of input data may not be numeric, e.g., categorical features, text data, etc. It is necessary to transform those inputs into

a numerical format amenable to computations. This procedure requires for the data type to have already been checked; otherwise an error could be raised.

- **Record linkage:** it is necessary to identify unique input patterns across a vertical partition, such that information about the same pattern/example can be joined in the global training process. Therefore this step is specific to a vertical partitioning of the data.
- **Data pre-processing:** it might be necessary to apply some data transformations to get the data ready for the learning process. This kind of pre-processing is implemented in MMLL by defining a *pre-processing object* which is sent to the participants such that they can locally transform their data. This approach is feasible whenever the pre-processing definition does not depend on any global traits of the data. MMLL comes with some predefined pre-processing models but, if a more elaborate “ad hoc” one is needed, it must be provided by the end user. This procedure expects the data to have previously been transformed into a numerical format, otherwise an error would be raised.
- **A priori data alignment estimation:** it is important to get a preliminary characterization of the available data regarding its suitability for the task at hand, such that some participants that are potentially far from the minimum alignment requirements can be excluded even before the beginning of the training process. In any case, MMLL does not make any decision about participant suppression directly, it simply provides the data alignment estimations, and the Data Scientist which is designing the Machine Learning process is free to accept or reject those users. As already mentioned, further security mechanisms during training will be provided in the context of WP5.
- **Data normalization:** Once that a set of “fair” participants have been identified, the data must be subject to a normalization process. Essentially, this can be considered as extra pre-processing, but in this case some of the parameters of the pre-processing object are dependent on the whole training dataset. A good example is the requirement for the data normalization to have zero mean and unit standard deviation for every feature. Before transforming the data at every participant, the global mean and global standard deviation values must be computed and inserted in the pre-processing object before sending it to the participants.
- **Dimensionality reduction:** After checking that every worker has the correct type of data, and such data is adequately normalized to be operated in a common training procedure, it is sometimes the case that the input dimension is too high for successful model training. The inconvenience of a high input dimension is twofold. On one side, finding a reasonable solution in a very high dimensional space with few

training patterns is sometimes difficult (curse of dimensionality). Think, for instance, of a text classification problem where the input dimension can be as high as 100,000 but we may have only a few hundred labelled training documents. On the other side, a large input dimension usually implies larger models, and a larger exchange of parameters across the network, which usually slows down the training process. We provide some dimensionality reduction procedures that can alleviate these problems in the subsequent training process: Principal Component Analysis, Random (Full or Sparse) Projection, Sparse Frequency Selection, and Greedy feature selection.

In what follows, we will describe how to use these functionalities in the MMLL context.

3.1 Input/output data type verification

As a part of the task specification, it is necessary to define the input and output data description, such that any potential participant can understand the required type of data before participating (joining) a given training process. Any participant joining a task should provide data according to that specification. However, mistakes can happen (unintentionally or on purpose), and it is safer to check that the provided data is in accordance with the data type description.

An example of input data description format (Python3 dictionary) could be as follows:

```
input_data_description = {  
    "NI": 3,  
    "input_types": [  
        {"type": "num", "name": "age"},  
        {"type": "cat", "name": "workclass",  
         "values": ["Private", "Self-emp", "Federal-gov",  
                  "Local-gov", "State-gov", "Without-pay", "Never-worked"]},  
        {"type": "bin", "name": "PhD"}  
    ]  
}
```

We observe several fields:

- **NI**: “Number of inputs”, declares the number of input features to be used.
- **Input_types**: describes the type of every input feature. In the above example we have included three features with different types that can be combined to build a

multi-feature input vector. **num** type refers to any feature with a numerical value, **bin** refers to input features that only take 0/1 values and **cat** refers to a categorical feature that can take any of the values listed in the **values** field.

Examples of input patterns that abide by this data description are:

[43, 'Private', 0]

[56, 'State-gov', 1]

Other input types are also possible, such as “**text**”, “**bow**” or “**image**” as illustrated in some of the examples below, but in this case a single input feature is allowed.

Also, a target description must also be provided, for instance, if the target value is numeric:

```
target_data_description= {  
    "NT": 1,  
    "output_types": [{"type": "num", "name": "income",  
                      "definition": "Income in K€"}]}
```

where **NT** declares the number of targets, and **output_types** lists the type of each one using a syntax analogous to that of **input_types** above.

Some examples of valid targets are:

[23]

[58]

In what follows we will illustrate the data check process in MMLL. We assume that instances of the Master Node and Worker node objects (**mn**, **wn**) are already available, e.g.:

At the Master:

```
from MMLL.nodes.MasterNode import MasterNode  
  
mn = MasterNode(<params>)
```

At every Worker:

```
from MMLL.nodes.WorkerNode import WorkerNode
```

```
wn = WorkerNode(<params>
wn.run()
```

Once all participants are in a running state, the Master node can orchestrate the required distributed operations on their data. In this case, to apply the **data type check**, we simply execute:

```
errors, bad_workers = mn.check_data_at_workers(input_data_description,
                                              target_data_description)
```

The returned parameters are:

- **errors**: it indicates whether any kind of error has occurred at the Workers. If the process has run without any problem, the result is *None*.
- **bad_workers**: list of participants with incorrect input/data type of data. If all participants' data is correct, the result is *None*.

Once the list of non-conforming Workers is available, the Master node may decide to disconnect them from the learning process, so that they will not receive any further message:

```
mn.terminate_workers(bad_workers)
```

Alternatively, the client connector may decide on any other strategy about them, but they cannot participate in the training process with the current data they provided.

3.2 Data conversion to numeric format

There are some types of input data whose type is naturally non-numerical. Examples are categorical features or texts/documents.

3.2.1 Categorical features

This transformation is needed whenever categorical features are present. The implemented method is the standard “one-hot encoding” procedure, which transforms any categorical

input into a collection of binary inputs (as many possible values as there are in the categorical feature). One example of such encoding is as follows:

"Local-gov" -> 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0

"Unemployed" -> 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0

In this example, every categorical feature is replaced by 9 binary features. This method takes as input the *input data description* and transforms data at the Workers:

```
data2num_transformer, new_input_data_description, errors_data2num =  
mn.data2num_transform_workers(input_data_description)
```

It returns the new data description after the transformation. Also, the list of potential errors is obtained, as well as a transformer object ready to be applied to a local dataset, which must also conform to the input/output data description format.

```
X_test = data2num_transformer.transform(X_test)
```

3.2.2 Texts/documents

Texts or documents are a common input data in many machine learning tasks (translation, text classification, document self-organization, sentiment analysis, concept extraction, etc.) They can be provided in different stages of transformation. In what follows we describe the most popular ones.

- **Plain text:** This is the most natural encoding for a text content, since it simply comprises of the sequence of words contained in a document. One pattern example could be:

"The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog"

- **Bag of words (bow):** It is rather common to transform the raw texts into a format which is closer to numeric. Many intermediate steps are usually applied: punctuation removal, stemming, stop words elimination, tokenization, etc. It exceeds the scope of this document to serve as an introduction to Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques, and there are very powerful libraries implementing those transformations (e.g. Natural

Language Toolkit (NLTK) [NLTK]). The interested reader may refer to [Vajjala_2020] for an introduction to the topic. We will skip that part and assume that these transformations can be easily carried out by the user using any standard library. We will describe, however, the **bow** format, which is a measure of the frequency of appearance of the words in the text. MMLL accepts texts in bow format (python3 dictionary) as input. For instance, the bow for the raw text in the previous example, would be the following:

```
{'the': 2, 'quick': 1, "brown": 1, "fox": 1, "jumps":1, "over":1, "lazy":1, "dog":1 }
```

A more realistic bow example, obtained after processing a technological brief text, could be as follows:

```
{'using': 1, 'ws': 5, 'back': 1, 'it': 4, 'could': 1, 'mywinobj': 6, 'the': 17, 'version': 1, 'new': 1, 'object': 8, 'calling': 5, 'jun': 1, 'my': 11, 'so': 4, 'be': 3, 'do': 18, 'wait': 2, 'with': 1, 'data': 2, 'to': 8, 'however': 1, 'invoking': 1, 'mycallingprog': 1, 'shownormal': 1, 'statement': 2, 'processed': 1, 'void': 1, 'some': 2, 'show': 2, 'thanks': 1, 'is': 3, 'window': 17, 'ps': 2, 'class': 1, 'may': 1, 'want': 1, 'lord': 1, 'invokes': 1, 'any': 2, 'function': 1, 'there': 1, 'sw': 1, 'control': 2, 'bc': 1, 'mywindow': 3, 'ms': 2, 'until': 2, 'would': 2, 'sdk': 1, 'other': 1, 'specified': 1, 'next': 2, 'makewindow': 1, 'didn': 1, 'that': 3, 'appreciated': 1, 'objectwindows': 2, 'windows': 4, 'when': 1, 'won': 1, 'trying': 1, 'twindow': 3, 'here': 2, 'and': 2, 'public': 1, 'keeps': 1, 'getapplication': 1, 'gives': 1, 'can': 2, 'look': 1, 'keywords': 1, 'closed': 2, 'from': 1, 'execute': 1, 'way': 1, 'program': 6, 'style': 1, 'up': 3, 'like': 2, 'talk': 1, 'popupwindow': 1, 'through': 1, 'help': 2, 'give': 2, 'executing': 1, 'get': 3, 'in': 35, 'after': 1 }
```

As it can be observed, the potential vocabulary for a given task can be extremely high, not only due to the large number of words in a given language, but because many other terms such as “*getapplication*”, “*sdk*” or “*mywinobj*” may be produced as a result of the pre-processing applied on the texts. The general objective is to obtain an input numerical matrix that represents all that language information and that can serve as input for the subsequent machine learning processes. Usually, such a matrix has as many rows as documents and as many columns as different terms in the bow’s vocabulary. In a general case, such numerical matrix has a huge (column) size and is very sparse (most entries are zero), however, it is a necessary intermediate representation before applying other transformations, such as dimensionality reduction. Therefore, to obtain the numerical matrix, we first

need to obtain a common vocabulary for all Workers. This can be done in MMLL as follows:

```
vocabulary, df_dict = mn.get_vocabulary_workers(input_data_description)
```

As a result, we obtain the unique vocabulary, common to all Workers, as well as the document frequency parameter, i.e., in how many documents a given term is present. The next step is to compute the numerical matrix, which contains the term-frequency-inverse-document frequency (tfidf) information:

```
from MMLL.preprocessors.tfidf_matrix import tfidf_matrix_model

tfidf_extractor = tfidf_matrix_model(vocabulary, df_dict,
input_data_description)

errors_tfidf = mn.preprocess_data_at_workers(tfidf_extractor)

new_input_data_description =
tfidf_extractor.new_input_data_description
```

As usual, the returned parameters are the new input data description, the list of potential errors and the transforming object such that the same *tfidf* matrix structure can be obtained on any other input local data:

```
X_tfidf_test = tfidf_extractor.transform(X_bow_test)
```

3.2.3 Images

Although images are usually represented by numeric values, they have an N -dimensional nature (usually three-dimensional, but also multi-spectral), that complicates their use in ML processes. In some models, such as convolutional neural networks, they can be directly fed to the model, but in some other cases, it is convenient to reshape them or convert them into a vector representation. We have added some pre-processing methods for reshaping and image to vector conversion, as described in the next sub-section.

3.3 Data pre-processing

We will describe here some of the standard data pre-processing techniques implemented in MMLL. These techniques share a common characteristic: they can be applied at every

Worker irrespectively of the data available at other Workers and hence they are POM-independent.

3.3.1 Logarithmic scale transformation

This pre-processing is useful when the dynamical range of the input features is very large, such that a given variation around zero is completely occluded by the large variations at other parts of the input range. Imagine for instance that a given feature can take the values 1, 2, 5, 25.000, 25.100. If we normalize the values using the same scale, the details in the first values are almost lost. A logarithmic transformation preserves the details for small inputs, and translates the large input variations into a more manageable range. In the next figure we show the logarithmic pre-processor function definition on a (-10, 10) range (subfigure A), and in the (-100, 100) range (subfigure B).

Figure 12: Logarithmic preprocessor

We see that in both cases input values are univocally mapped to a more reasonable range (within ± 10), less prone to produce instabilities in the training algorithm. The use within MMLL would be as follows:

```
from MMLL.preprocessors.logscale import logscale_model
prep_logscale = logscale_model(input_data_description)
errors_logscale = mn.preprocess_data_at_workers(prepare_logscale)
X_log_tst = prep_logscale.transform(X_tst)
```

Another advantage of the logscale pre-processor is that it limits the effect of very unusual input features taking very large values due to a measurement error or intentional tampering (outliers).

3.3.2 Outlier clipping

If we desire to directly control the potential outliers in the dataset by limiting the maximal value that a feature can take without modifying the rest of feature values, we can use the outlier clipping pre-processing. Its operation is as indicated in Figure 12 below, for two different threshold values (4 in A, 2 in B).

Figure 13: Outlier clipping preprocessor

```
from MMLL.preprocessors.outlier_clipping import outlier_clipping_model
times_sigma = 1.5
prep_outlier_clipping = outlier_clipping_model(
    input_data_description, times_sigma=times_sigma)
# or using an absolute value
absolute_th = 2.0
prep_outlier_clipping = outlier_clipping_model(
    input_data_description, absolute_th=absolute_th)
errors_outlier_clipping = mn.preprocess_data_at_workers(
    prep_outlier_clipping)
X_outlier_tst = prep_outlier_clipping.transform(X_tst)
```

As can be observed in the above code, the method receives as a parameter the threshold value to apply. We can use an absolute value or provide a threshold relative to the standard deviation of the data (1.5σ in the above example).

Any other “ad hoc” pre-processing method that is specific to a particular use case needs to be provided as an external transforming object to MMLL, since it is not possible to foresee and implement any arbitrary potential pre-processing method that is going to be required by some task.

3.3.3 Image pre-processing

3.3.3.1 Image reshaping and vectorization

In this pre-processing scenario every training pattern is an image (one or more two-dimensional arrays, one per channel, e.g., grayscale images have one channel, RGB images have 3 channels, and multispectral images may have an unlimited number of channels). The first provided transforming method is intended for reshaping every channel of the image into a given number of row/column pixels. An alternative is to transform the entire image into a vector, such that if an image is $C \times M \times N$ (C being the number of channels), the resulting vector has shape $1 \times (C \times M \times N)$, and can be stored as a single row of a data matrix.

3.3.3.2 Deep Learning Image Pre-processing using AlexNet.

In this case, the input image is processed using a general purpose predefined Deep Learning model, in this case, the well-known AlexNet network [Krizhevsky_2012]. This model is able to extract from the images a set of visually relevant features that can be used in pattern recognition tasks. Since AlexNet is a general purpose model initially trained for image classification of a particular dataset, some of the extracted features may not be highly relevant for the task at hand. Therefore, this technique is performed better when combined with a task oriented feature selection mechanism before feeding the information to the training algorithm. The architecture of the network described in [Krizhevsky2012], used to transform any image into a vector with size 1000, is as follows:

Figure 14: Alexnet architecture representation, from [missinglink.ai].

The usage of the Deep Learning Pre-processor in MMLL is as follows:

```
dl_transformer, new_input_data_description, errors_deep_learning =  
mn.deep_learning_transform_workers(input_data_description)
```

Also, if this transformer is to be used on a local dataset:

```
X_dl_test = dl_transformer.transform(X_test)
```

3.4 A priori data alignment estimation

In an “a priori” data alignment estimation (prior to the actual model training) it is not possible to fully evaluate the relevance of a given dataset for a particular model without actually assessing the difference in the resulting model with and without that data contribution. In a centralized setting it would be possible (affordable) to run extensive simulations to identify the best combination of data contributions for a given task but in a distributed setup where training is usually a very costly process, it is not possible to run multiple experiments and we have to rely on assumptions about the type of data that are more suitable for a given problem.

In a traditional setup, where all data is available for analysis without any kind of restriction apart from the computational one, the data alignment estimation task could be stated as the problem of verifying that the different dataset partitions share a common (or at least similar) joint distribution. Actually, the main objective at this early stage is to detect distributions that significantly differ from the general distribution of the available data for the task. If data from user "0" can be described as $\{\mathbf{x}_p, y_p\}^0, p = 1, \dots, N_0$, we can assume that the patterns associated to user "0" come from a given joint distribution $p_0(\mathbf{x}, y)$. We could apply the same reasoning to the data coming from the other users $p_1(\mathbf{x}, y), p_2(\mathbf{x}, y)$, etc., including the one intended to provide a reference: $p_R(\mathbf{x}, y)$. Therefore, we could state the data alignment estimation problem as one of computing the distances among those distributions: the users with distributions closer to the reference are considered "aligned", and we assume that they will contribute positively to the training process. Misaligned users should be removed from the training set. Hence, in this problem statement a reference distribution is needed. Basically there are two options:

- Build the reference using a local dataset, known to be trustworthy and with a distribution similar to that of the test set.
- When such local dataset is not available, a reference has to be built upon consensus among the distributions from the participants. Obviously, this approach will fail if there is a majority of participants providing data not aligned with the test set.

Classical examples of such kind of distances are, among many other, the Kullback–Leibler divergence [Kullback_1951], the Hellinger distance [Hellinger_1909], the total variation distance [Chatterjee_2008], the Jensen–Shannon divergence [Schütze_1999] or the Wasserstein metric (earth mover's distance) [Rüschendorf_2001]. However, in the MUSKETEER context, we do not have unlimited access to the data of the different participants, and the above mentioned estimations of distance between distributions are not computable under this setting. We will have to restrict ourselves to computing distances among one or more statistics vectors (SVs) that preserve the privacy/confidentiality of the data. We will assume, therefore, that some SVs can be constructed at every user location and that distances on them can be obtained at the Master node without compromising the confidentiality of the raw data. We will propose here some SVs, but others could be added. We propose to compute the following statistics:

- **meanx**: mean values of the input features
- **medianx**: median values of the input features
- **stdx**: standard deviation values of the input features
- **skewx**: skewness values of the input features
- **kurx**: kurtosis values of the input features

- **perc25**: percentile 25 values of the input features
- **perc75**: percentile 75 values of the input features
- **staty**: statistics of the target value, such as mean, std, skewness or kurtosis.
- **covx**: covariance values of the input features
- **rxxy**: cross-correlation values among inputs and target

In all cases, these vectors are normalized to have unit norm. Once the statistics have been computed at the workers, cosine similarity distances (computable using a dot product) can be obtained at the Master node without explicit knowledge of the statistics at the Workers. Therefore the alignment value depicted in Figure 15 is computed as a dot product of unit norm vectors. Depending on the POM, the method to evaluate the dot product can be different. For instance, in POM4 the SVs from the workers are received encrypted, and the dot product is computed using the homomorphic properties of the encryption scheme, whereas in POM5 the reference SV is sent encrypted to the workers, which can also compute the distance and return it to the Master node, and in POM 6 any Secure Dot Product (SDP) can be used for that operation. In what follows we show some benchmark experiments that reveal which are the most appropriate ones.

Figure 15 Results of the proposed data alignment estimation. In (a) 5 users providing fair (aligned) data are present. In (b) users 1, 2, and 4 provide non-aligned data (random data, random targets)

We observe how the distances measured on the different SVs evidence discrepancies when the data is not aligned. The Total Alignment index for inputs is TA_x, for targets is TA_y, for input-outputs is TA_{xy} and the final TA value summarizes them all (green box), such that by applying a threshold on that value it is possible to filter out unwanted participants before actually training the model.

In MMLL we provide this Data Alignment estimation functionality, and it can be used as follows:

```
# We select the statistics we want to use in the data alignment estimation
stats_list = ['rxy', 'mx', 'medianx', 'statsy', 'perc25']

# If we provide a reference dataset, it is used to compute the reference
statistics otherwise a consensus criterion is used

dv = mn.get_data_value_apriori(stats_list, X_ref, y_ref)
```

After this preliminary detection of miss-aligned datasets, any procedure provided in WP5 (Security and Trustworthiness) could improve the detection of malicious users trying to interfere in the normal training process in more subtle ways (data poisoning, evasion attacks, etc.).

3.5 Data normalization

The goal here is to transform the data at the Workers such that they are expressed in a format that usually favours the learning process. For instance, some learning algorithms are better behaved when the input features have global zero mean and unit standard deviation, or re-scaled to fit into a given min/max range. These transformations can be applied locally at every Worker using a pre-processing object, following a procedure similar to that described in previous sections. However, the parameters of that object need to be estimated using the all (globally) available training data. In other words, before actually transforming the data it is necessary to carry out the following steps:

- Compute global parameters to be used by the normalizer (global mean, global standard deviation, global minimum value, global maximum value).
- Build a normalizer object and send it to the workers so they can locally pre-process their data.
- Use the same object locally to transform any other dataset (e.g. a test dataset).

Summarizing, the code to run from the Master Node is as follows:

```
normalization_type = 'global_mean_std'

# or

normalization_type = 'global_min_max'

normalizer = mn.normalizer_fit_transform_workers(
```

```
input_data_description, normalization_type)  
X_normalized_test = normalizer.transform(X_test)
```

3.6 Dimensionality reduction

The goal here is to obtain a data representation with a reduced number of input features, which can be either a selection of some of them or a transformation of all of them into a reduced subset of inputs (linear combination of inputs resulting in a smaller dimension subspace). Under some circumstances this reduction process is possible without losing information because the inputs are highly correlated or, even it may happen that some of them are irrelevant for the task at hand. In other cases, a trade-off between input dimension reduction and information loss is generally observed. In what follows we describe some of the implemented dimensionality reduction techniques.

3.6.1 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

PCA analysis is a well-known and established technique for dimensionality reduction, largely analysed in the literature [Bishop_2007]. As a result, a given data matrix \mathbf{X} is expressed using a Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) as follows:

$$\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{V}^T$$

where \mathbf{S} is a diagonal matrix of singular values sorted in decreasing order, \mathbf{U} is a unitary matrix and the columns of \mathbf{V} are the principal directions/axes. In the above expression, the rows of matrix \mathbf{US} represent the principal components (scores) of \mathbf{X} (projections with respect to the main Principal Component axis represented in \mathbf{V}). So, if we want to retain the main P components of a dataset, we must retain the first P columns of \mathbf{V} as principal directions (\mathbf{V}_P submatrix), and obtain the corresponding new scores by projecting the dataset onto the principal directions by computing the dot product $\langle \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{V}_P \rangle$.

This is the standard approach to follow in a centralized setting, where all data (\mathbf{X}) is stored at the same place. However, in a distributed setting with confidentiality constraints, we do not have access to the full data matrix \mathbf{X} . In this case, we can take advantage of a relationship between the SVD of \mathbf{X} and the eigenvalue decomposition of the – centred-covariance matrix as follows:

$$\mathbf{C}_{xx} = \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{X} / (n-1)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_{xx} = \mathbf{V} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{V}^T$$

We can easily see the relationship:

$$\mathbf{C}_{xx} = \mathbf{V} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{U} \mathbf{S} \mathbf{V}^T / (n-1) = \mathbf{V} \mathbf{S}^2 / (n-1) \mathbf{V}^T$$

This way it is possible to obtain the main principal directions (first columns in \mathbf{V}) by either decomposing the data matrix or its covariance. We will prefer to operate on the latter, since it can be computed on a globally distributed data partition without actually sharing the values in the data matrix, and hence we preserve data confidentiality. In order to do it we take advantage that, under a horizontal partitioning, the global data matrix can be represented as:

$$\mathbf{X}^T = [\mathbf{X}_1^T, \mathbf{X}_2^T, \mathbf{X}_3^T, \dots, \mathbf{X}_m^T, \dots, \mathbf{X}_M^T]^T$$

such that local correlation matrices can be computed at every participant as:

$$\mathbf{R}_{xx,1} = \mathbf{X}_1^T \mathbf{X}_1; \quad \mathbf{R}_{xx,2} = \mathbf{X}_2^T \mathbf{X}_2; \quad \mathbf{R}_{xx,3} = \mathbf{X}_3^T \mathbf{X}_3; \quad \mathbf{R}_{xx,m} = \mathbf{X}_m^T \mathbf{X}_m; \quad \mathbf{R}_{xx,M} = \mathbf{X}_M^T \mathbf{X}_M$$

and, after applying a direct aggregation method or a secure one under the round-robin protocol, we can obtain at the Master the covariance matrix:

$$\mathbf{C}_{xx} = (\mathbf{R}_{xx,1} + \mathbf{R}_{xx,2} + \mathbf{R}_{xx,3} + \dots + \mathbf{R}_{xx,m} + \dots + \mathbf{R}_{xx,M}) / (n-1)$$

and perform the corresponding eigenvalue analysis to define the PCA transformer object, to be sent to the workers and also to be used locally. Therefore, the PCA analysis requires access by the Master node to the global covariance matrix, but the local data is not revealed and even the local covariances can be kept confidential if the round-robin aggregation method is used. The use in the MUSKETEER context would be as follows:

```
aggregation_type = 'direct'

NF = 40 # number of features

pca_transformer, new_input_data_description, workers_errors =
    mn.pca_fit_transform_workers(input_data_description,
                                aggregation_type, NF)

Xval = pca_transformer.transform(Xval)
```

It is an open issue to decide how many Principal Components we must retain to achieve a good approximation to the original data matrix. The eigenvalue analysis provides us with a quantification of the importance value of every component, such that we can decide where to fix a threshold. Such profile of ranked principal values may have a shape analogous to the one shown in the next Figure:

Figure 16 Ranked eigenvalues for a sample PCA decomposition of two data matrices. Income dataset in (a) with 111 input features and MNIST dataset in (b) with 784 input features.

We observe that the largest contribution is always obtained from the first principal components, and the eigenvalue profile decreases with the number of components. In both cases, the last components represent a zero contribution to the matrix reconstruction (which means that they are fully superfluous since they can be represented as a linear combination of previously selected principal components) and hence they can be eliminated without information loss. For the remaining components we observe the trade-off between approximation error and number of final input dimension.

3.6.2 Feature selection

3.6.2.1 Target oriented greedy selection

Many feature selection procedures exist in the literature [Chandrashekar_2014], but most of them require full access to the training data and, in some cases, they entail to fit the model many times with different input combinations. In other approaches, a cost function that leads to sparse solutions can be used [Deng_2015], such that the final model weights become zero for many of the input features, thereby yielding a feature selection outcome. However, our MUSKETEER setting has many restrictions that hamper the application of the above mentioned methods. First of all, the training data at the different participants cannot be directly accessed. On the other hand, computational and communications restrictions apply, such that it is not possible to run a large number of distributed optimizations and sparse methods cannot be applied because the whole set of inputs cannot be used (the latter being, in general, too large).

We propose here a Greedy Feature Selection method that follows MUSKETEER restrictions but relies on several assumptions: the global covariance data matrix and cross-correlation

vector must be shared with the Master node, a linear model is used for the selection, and a local validation dataset is available at the Master node. If we fulfil these requirements, the following procedure can be implemented at a reasonable computational and communication cost:

- Compute the global self-correlation matrix \mathbf{R}_{xx} and cross-correlation vector \mathbf{r}_{xy} following any of the approaches already explained (direct or round-robin aggregation). A linear model \mathbf{w} using only a subset S of features is easily found by solving:

$$\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{R}_{xx}[S, S]^{-1} \mathbf{r}_{xy}[S]$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{xx}[S, S]$ is the submatrix obtained by extracting from \mathbf{R}_{xx} the rows and columns listed in the set S , and $\mathbf{r}_{xy}[S]$ is the sub-vector obtained by retaining the rows in S .

- Iteratively select the most relevant features by solving local linear model optimizations:
 - o Select as a first feature the one providing the best performance on the validation set and add it to the set of selected features $S_{\text{selected}} = \{f_{\text{best}}\}$
 - o For each of the remaining input features f_k , compute the performance (Mean Square Error (MSE), for instance) of a model trained on the set $S_{\text{selected}} \cup \{f_k\}$
 - o Find the best performing combination and add feature f_k to the set of selected ones.
 - o Repeat the process until the desired number of features is found.

Even though this procedure may be suboptimal because it relies on a linear model for selection, it has shown good performance in practice. The selected input features can be later used to train a better nonlinear model. The use in the MUSKETEER context would be as follows:

```
aggregation_type = 'direct'

NF = 40

ranked_inputs, performance_evolution = mn.rank_features_gfs (
    Xval, yval, input_data_description, aggregation_type, NF)

from MMLL.preprocessors.feature_extract import feature_extract_model

feature_extractor = feature_extract_model(
    ranked_inputs, input_data_description)
```

```
new_input_data_description , errors_feature_extract =  
    mn.preprocess_data_at_workers(feature_extractor)  
Xval = feature_extractor.transform(Xval)
```

As an example, we illustrate here the MML feature selection process on the Income and MNIST databases.

Figure 17 Ranked features with the Greedy Feature Selection approach. Income dataset in (a) with 111 input features and MNIST dataset in (b) with 784 input features.

If we observe the performance curves we see that they reach a relative plateau, and after that they even grow again, possibly due to an overfitting effect. Therefore, for the Income dataset it would be convenient to retain around 40 features and 200 in the MNIST case, i.e., the points where their performance curves reach a steady value.

3.6.2.2 Sparse data frequency selection

In some cases a very large data matrix is encountered, but the sparsity of that matrix is very large. This is a common situation in many Natural Language Processing problems, but it may also be found in other contexts. It is very common that some features are only present in very few training patterns, and some other features are present in almost all patterns. Both cases reflect little relevance of that feature for any task, so a straightforward approach for selecting relevant features is based on their frequency of appearance. This pre-processing should be interpreted as a first step towards a preliminary complexity reduction in the problem, a complementary feature selection should be carried out afterwards. The usage in MML is as follows:

```

max_freq = 0.90 # We remove features present in > 90% of the samples
NF = 1000 # We retain NF features, the maximal assumable dimension,
# sorted by frequency.

freq_feature_extractor, new_input_data_description =
    mn.get_feat_freq_transformer(input_data_description, max_freq, NF)
errors_ffe = mn.preprocess_data_at_workers(freq_feature_extractor)
Xtst_ffe = freq_feature_extractor.transform(Xtst)
    
```

3.6.3 Random projection

Another alternative when the data matrix is very large but non sparse is to apply a Random Projection (RP) technique. The Johnson-Lindenstrauss lemma [Lindenstrauss] states that vectors in a very high-dimensional space can be linearly mapped to a lower (but still relatively high, i.e., the number of projected dimensions should be higher than $8 \log(F)/\epsilon$ to preserve distances with precision ϵ with respect to the original dimensions, F .) dimensional space while still preserving the original distances. Therefore, a Random Projection could serve to map data to an intermediate space with a dimension that is low enough to make the subsequent applications feasible, for instance a feature selection or dimensionality reduction method [Bingham_2001][Menon_2017]. The application of RP has been depicted in Figure 18 below. The interpretation is that a direct application of PCA or any feature selection in the original large dimensional data space is not affordable, while it is feasible in the intermediate space.

Figure 18: Random projection as an intermediate step towards low dimensional space representations.

In what follows we will describe the two main Random Projection methods: full projection and sparse projection.

3.6.3.1 Full Random projection

In this case, to map a data matrix \mathbf{X} with size $(N \times F)$, where N is the number of training patterns and F is the number of features, into a lower dimensional data matrix \mathbf{Z} with size $(N \times L)$, it is necessary to create a linear mapping matrix \mathbf{M} with size $F \times L$, such that $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{X} \mathbf{M}$. In this case, it is common to obtain the values of \mathbf{M} as draws from a Normal distribution with zero mean and variance equal to $1/L$.

```
intermediate_dimension = 500

from MMLL.preprocessors.random_projection import random_projection_model

random_projector = random_projection_model(
    input_data_description, intermediate_dimension,
    projection_type='full') # Random projection, full

Xval_RP = random_projector.transform(Xval)

errors_RP = mn.preprocess_data_at_workers(random_projector)
```


(a)

(b)

Figure 19: Example of PCA after a Random projection. Three clusters of data in different input dimensions are found with PCA after projecting into an intermediate space with dimension 100. F=500 in (a), F=10.000 in (b), F=500.000 in (c), F=1.000.000 in (d).

3.6.3.2 Sparse Random projection

In this case, the size of the involved matrices are the same as in the previous section, but the mapping matrix \mathbf{M} is sparse, and it is generated such that non-sparse components ratio is equal to $1/\sqrt{F}$.

```

intermediate_dimension = 500

from MMLL.preprocessors.random_projection import random_projection_model

random_projector = random_projection_model(
    input_data_description, intermediate_dimension,
    projection_type='sparse') # Random projection, sparse

Xval_RP = random_projector.transform(Xval)

errors_RP = mn.preprocess_data_at_workers(random_projector)
    
```

4 Privacy preserving record linkage

As already discussed, in the vertical partitioning scenario it is necessary to look for a connection between different records in different locations, such that their distributed features can be combined into a single record (at least from a machine learning point of view, since the actual data is never moved around). It is very common to use universal identifiers to establish such relationship, e.g., Social Security number, Passport ID, full name, etc., and these are optimal since they should be unique identifiers. However, they bear private information and therefore cannot be shared for record linkage. A rather straightforward approach is to transform the unique IDs into a different string of characters that preserves the identification capabilities but completely hides the private data. This can be done by using a Secure Hash Algorithm (SHA), which transforms the unique identifier into an (also unique) string that completely hides the original ID. In our implementation we have used the SHA-256 algorithm (256 bits), which is the method used in the Bitcoin network [Luan_2020]. Three examples of ID transformation using SHA-256 are shown next. The resulting ids are named “hashids”:

ID = “Johann Sebastian Bach 5235432462356”

hashid = a79b5920a063492fd7e38a1dd13058df4dd95e9905b7e55cf6a085da05354bb6

ID = “Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart 919654301452123”

hashid = 899965def662185fd3f836b1d27e908b1f5fa1354ca04a047a3d358e32d95389

ID = “Antonio Lucio Vivaldi 6124309273123”

hashid = 7214d849c7ee7eb6fd39b4ab65db863bdd78cea9724d3ad96ea489ca3983e4cb

These one-way hash algorithms are vulnerable to pre-image and collision attacks via look-up-table comparison with precomputed hash values. Short IDs are more vulnerable to this kind of attacks since they are most probably present in the look-up tables (e.g. “123456”). Therefore it is advisable to use an ID that is as long as possible. For instance, the IDs indicated in the above example are built using a numerical ID plus a name, since it is much less likely that they are found in a precomputed table. In any case, the SHA-256 hash function can easily be replaced by any other more secure one directional hashing function, if deemed necessary.

Therefore, before training any model under a vertical data partitioning, it is necessary to carry out the following steps:

- **Compute a common list of unique “hashids”** by gathering information from all participants. In the direct communication case, the Master node can receive the list of hashids available at each participant, but it is also possible to initiate a secure accumulation process using the round-robin protocol. After completing this step, the Master node has a list of unique hashids, plus a count of how many participants have data corresponding to every hashid. We can decide at this point whether to build an exhaustive list of unique hashids or only retain those hashids with features in all participants.
- **Transform the data at workers** such that data matrices are built at every participant, the row identification is the same in all of them, and coincides with the ordered list of hashids. Depending on the availability of input features for every hashid at every participant we can reach two different situations. The first one assumes that the hashid list includes identifiers that have a feature contribution for every participant, and therefore the resulting data matrices are full. On the other hand, if we consider all possible hashids, it may happen that a given participant cannot provide an input feature for some of the unique hashids, and the resulting data matrices may have missing data at certain coordinates.

This functionality is carried out in MUSKETEER as follows.

```
linkage_type = 'full' # Only full records are considered

linkage_type = 'join' # All data is joined, but missing values can be
present

input_data_description, target_data_description =

    mn.record_linkage_transform_workers(linkage_type)
```

Under the second scenario with missing data, it is necessary to perform a data imputation process before training a model, as explained in the next section.

4.1 Missing data imputation

As described in the previous section, as a result of the hashid synchronization process across participants in a vertical partitioning scenario, it may happen that the resulting data matrices have missing values at certain coordinates. This could also happen in a horizontal partition if the original data provided by every worker is already missing some values. A very simple yet suboptimal approach is simply to discard the incomplete training patterns, as done by default in many machine learning packages. However, it is also possible to try and not

discard any information, and reconstruct to some extent the missing data values. In an unrestricted centralized scenario there are many potential techniques for carrying out data imputation functionalities, which mainly estimate the most probable value given the other available inputs, i.e., gaining information from the global underlying data distribution [Kalton_1986][Rosenthal_2017]. The variety of available techniques in an unrestricted scenario is overwhelming (hot/cold deck imputation, mean imputation, non-negative matrix factorization, regression imputation, stochastic imputation, etc.) and it exceeds the scope of this project to explore all of them. In MUSKETEER we provide the mean data imputation technique, which can be implemented at every worker without requiring information from other workers. Additionally, this imputation technique is known to provide good results whenever there is little correlation among the different features [Faizan_2018]. The usage of mean imputation processor in MUSKETEER is as follows:

```
from MMLL.preprocessors.data_imputation import imputation_model_V
imputator = imputation_model_V(new_input_data_description)
errors_imputation = mn.preprocess_data_at_workers_V(imputator)
```

5 Data value estimation

One of the main estimation methods needed to deploy a data economy is that for Data Value Estimation (DVE), since any reward for the participants must be somehow related of the quality or utility of the provided data to the global training process. In WP6 a complete analysis of data economy scenarios will be carried out.

For illustration purposes, we have depicted in the Figure 20 the operation of simplified Data Alignment estimation and Data Value estimation approaches. As an example we observe that user number 3 offers a large amount of data, but its quality is low and therefore the reward should be smaller than for user No. 1 and user No. 2 (that provide better data quality), even considering the latter contribute with less data. User No. 4 also provides data, but it is detected as non-aligned and therefore it is considered as rubbish or poisoned data. User No. 4 should be excluded from the learning process, and obviously gets no reward in return.

Figure 20 The Data alignment/value estimation concept

We will restrict ourselves to the following operation scenarios under which a DVE process can be deployed:

- **“a Priori” Data Value Estimation (PDVE).** Under this scenario, a DVE is to be provided before actually training any particular model. This can be done using the Data Alignment Estimation (DAE) previously described but, obviously, the quality of the value estimations cannot be very high, because they are obtained based on general statistical measurements on the data which are, therefore, independent of the problem to be solved and only assess whether the corresponding datasets yield statistics close to some reference value. In MUSKETEER we provide methods for this “a priori” estimation combining the DAE with the amount of data provided by every participant.
- **“On-line” Data Value Estimation (ODVE).** In this case, the value estimation is obtained during a training process, by the exploration and comparison of the model updates received from every participant. This estimation is more accurate than the “a priori” one, since the information is extracted during the training process and the DVE is linked to a particular task and model. We will provide here the general framework for the computation of ODVE, but the final implementation and evaluation is very dependent on a particular training method and task, and hence will be provided in WP4 and WP6.
- **Greedy “a posteriori” Data Value Estimation (GDVE).** This method is not an algorithm but rather a general procedure that can be applied to any task/model

whenever a performance value exists and many training instances with different input data combinations can be carried out.

In the next subsections we will describe in more detail each one of the proposed schemes.

5.1 “a Priori” Data Value Estimation (PDVE)

As already mentioned, this method directly relies on the Data Alignment Estimation described in Section 3.4, which measures the agreement between every participant’s data with a reference value, which can be computed using a locally available reference dataset or by a consensus approach among all the data from the participants. It is possible to tune the data value definition by selecting an adequate set of statistical measurements to build the Data Alignment estimation, for instance, paying more attention to one statistical aspect than another. As a second step, it is possible to further modify the Data Values by weighting them proportionally to the number of training patterns provided by every participant, although this last step is an open door to cheating by the participants, since they can provide an artificially increased amount of data patterns to get a higher data value estimation and hence a greater reward.

5.2 “On-line” Data Value Estimation (ODVE)

Under this scenario, the Data Value Estimation is computed during the training process of a particular Machine Learning model, such that the model update from every participant is used at every iteration to update the current data value estimation, hence the “on-line” term. Therefore the algorithm described here must be imbricated with the model update steps during training such that every time the aggregator receives updates from the participants, their data value is also updated. Since this is highly dependent on the model being used, we will only describe here the data value updates assuming that contributions from every participant are available at every iteration. Let $\mathbf{w}^{(n)}$ represent the model parameters and $\Delta\mathbf{w}^{(n)}[m]$ the model updates received from participant “ m ”. We will also assume that at every iteration we have a reference value, $\mathbf{r}^{(n)}$, that indicates a good direction towards the optimal solution. As already mentioned, this reference value can be obtained using a local reference dataset or by consensus among all the received contributions. The above described scenario has been depicted in Figure 21 below, showing the available measurements at step n .

Figure 21: Data Value estimation using ODVE.

The alignment value for the m^{th} user $a^{(n)}[m]$ is defined as the rectified cosine distance between the reference vector and the negative of the gradient contributed from that worker:

$$a^{(n)}[m] = R \left(\frac{\langle -\nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{w}}}^{(n)}[m], \mathbf{r}^{(n)} \rangle}{\|\nabla_{\hat{\mathbf{w}}}^{(n)}[m]\| \cdot \|\mathbf{r}^{(n)}\|} \right)$$

where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ represents a dot product, $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm and $R(x) = \max(0, x)$ is the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) function. Therefore, the alignment value computed in the above expression is maximal and equal to 1 when both reference $\mathbf{r}^{(n)}$ and the negative gradient are fully aligned (linearly dependent), and it is zero when they are orthogonal or point in opposite directions. To reduce the estimation noise, we build the accumulated centred alignment $\mathbf{A}^{(n)}[m]$ value, that represents the overall accumulated contribution of every worker during the training process:

$$\mathbf{A}^{(n)}[m] = \mathbf{A}^{(n-1)}[m] + a^{(n)}[m] - \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \mathbf{A}^{(n-1)}[j]$$

with $\mathbf{A}^{(0)}[m] = 0$ for every worker, m .

We define the worker quality index by mapping the $A^{(n)}[m]$ values into the range (0, 1) using the sigmoid function $\sigma(\cdot)$:

$$q^{(n)}[m] = \sigma(A^{(n)}[m])$$

such that the $q^{(n)}[m]$ value of “good” workers should tend to 1 and to 0 for “bad” users. We define the share value $s^{(n)}[m]$ as the fraction of reward corresponding to every user:

$$s^{(n)}[m] = q^{(n)}[m] / \sum_{j=1}^M q^{(n)}[j]$$

Finally, the data value is estimated as the normalized product of these three terms:

- $q^{(n)}[m]$: the m^{th} user quality index
- $s^{(n)}[m]$: the m^{th} user share
- Q_m : the number of patterns provided by user m

therefore, the data value for user m at time n is:

$$v^{(n)}[m] = \frac{Q_m s^{(n)}[m] q^{(n)}[m]}{\sum_{j=1}^M Q_j s^{(n)}[j] q^{(n)}[j]}$$

In the following example we illustrate the Data Value Estimation in two scenarios with eleven participating users. In the first case, 7 fair users provide adequate data with different number of training patterns, and 4 of them provide either random data or wrong targets. In the second case, only 2 users are providing good data. The proposed GDVE scheme is able to provide estimations close to a data value computation based on the good data providers (dashed lines in Fig. 22)

Figure 22: Data Value estimation using GDVE algorithm when 11 users are present. In case (a) 7 users are fair, the other providing wrong data. In (b) only 2 users provide good data. Dashed lines represent the correct (gold standard) data value.

The described ODVE approach is available in MMLL as a method that receives the model updates from every participant, the reference value and returns the current Data Value estimation:

```
from MMLL.data_value import greedy_data_value_estimator
odve = online_data_value_estimator()
dv = mn.get_odve(odve, increments_from_participant, ref)
```

5.3 Greedy “a posteriori” Data Value Estimation (GDVE)

Under this scenario we directly use the performance attained when the target ML model is trained using a subset of different datasets from the participants. This procedure is able to provide optimal Data Value Estimations, since it is possible to measure the impact of every data contribution in the performance. Furthermore, this approach is able to decouple potential correlations in the data from different users in the sense that if a dataset has already been included in the final training set, then the new contributions must represent a quantitative improvement with respect to the data already available. However, it is very costly and time consuming, it requires to train the model many times and it also requires the use of training data that in the end may be discarded, hence receiving a null value/return. Since this is a general approach that can be implemented using any model/POM, we will simply illustrate it here using a classification task solved using a Logistic Classifier, and the performance is defined as the Area Under ROC Curve on a local validation dataset.

This Greedy Data Value Estimation approach would consist of the following steps:

1. Run a separate model training with data from every single user and identify the user that provides the best performance (it turns out to be user No. 3, in our case). Define the selected users set as {3}.
2. Run new training procedures on a combination of datasets: User 3 + User 0, User 3 + User 1, and User 3 + User 2, and measure the performance of each combination on the local validation set.
3. Choose the best performing combination (in this case, User 3 + User 0 is the best combination) and add that user to the selected users set: {3, 0}
4. Repeat steps 2-3 until all users have been evaluated and ranked. In our case User 1 produce a decrement in performance, so it has been excluded from the final Data

Value computation. The evolution of performance after adding users 3, 0 and 2 is depicted in the next Figure:

Figure 23: Performance evolution obtained using the Greedy Data Value Estimation approach.

In this scenario, we assume that the task proponent already has a functional model which provides a performance of $AUC=0.94$ and that such a model needs to be improved. The performance curve shown in Figure 23 represents the AUC values obtained when a new model is trained with the new datasets provided by the distributed participants (the task proponent could also participate in the process providing its local data). We observe how data from user "3" provides an improvement up to $AUC=0.95$ from the previous AUC of the reference dataset of 0.94 . The next user's data helps to improve the solution up to a value of $AUC = 0.956$, and finally, the third user provides a last improvement up to $AUC = 0.957$. Once this performance improvement curve is available, the GDVE approach would yield a data value estimation proportional to the improvement in performance produced by every contribution:

- User "3": provides improvement from $AUC=0.94$ to $AUC=0.95$, which represents an increment ratio of 0.0106
- User "0": provides improvement from $AUC=0.95$ to $AUC=0.956$, which represents an increment ratio of 0.00631
- User "2": provides improvement from $AUC=0.956$ to $AUC=0.957$, which represents an increment ratio of 0.00104

If we normalize the increment ratios to unit sum, the final GDVE values are as follows:

- User "3": $GDVE = 0.59$

- User "0": GDVE = 0.35
- User "2": GDVE = 0.058

Therefore, after this estimation procedure, the most valued user is No. 3, receiving a total of 60% of all reward, in second position user No. 0, receiving a 35%, and finally user No. 2 who only receives a 5.8% since its contribution to the improvement of the model is minimal.

The described GDVE approach is available at MMLL as a method that receives the model updates from every participant, the reference value and returns the current Data Value estimation:

```
current_auc_performance = 0.8 # The AUC attained by the current model
dv, best_workers = mn.get_data_value_aposteriori(X_ref, y_ref,
baseline_auc=Current_performance)
```

6 Software installation instructions

6.1 MUSKETEER Machine Learning Library

For the execution of the demos a proper Python environment has to be set up beforehand with all the dependencies correctly installed, including the MMLL library as well as the communications library used here (<https://github.com/IBM/pycloudmessenger/>). Although this information is present in the Github repository of the project (<https://github.com/Musketeer-H2020/MMLL>), the details of the configuration are going to be included also in this report.

The environment instructions are described for Anaconda, although any other tool for managing virtual environments could be used. First, we create a conda environment with the basic configuration and activate it:

```
conda create --name MMLL_demo python=3.7.4 git gmpy2==2.0.8 -c
defaults -c conda-forge --yes
conda activate MMLL_demo
```

The final step is to install the machine learning library and its dependencies (including `pycloudmessenger`):

```
pip install git+https://github.com/Musketeer-H2020/MMLL.git
```

6.2 MUSKETEER demos' setup

In order to be able to run the demos, the user has first to clone the repository for the demos. Working on the same virtual environment created in the above section, the user has to type:

```
git clone https://github.com/Musketeer-H2020/MMLL-demo.git
```

After that, navigate to the root directory of the repository and install the requirements:

```
cd MMLL-demo  
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

The repository for the demonstration has two important folders:

- **demos:** This folder contains all the demos available for the machine learning library, including the different algorithms already described in D4.4 and D4.6 as well as the pre-processing algorithms object of this deliverable. The different demos are organized by POMs and in order to be able to run them a json credentials file needs to be placed inside `demos/demo_pycloudmessenger`.
- **input_data:** Folder containing all the open datasets used for the different demos in pkl format. The datasets have to be downloaded from https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1-piNDL_tL6V4pCI-En02zeCEqL-dUUu?usp=sharing
- and placed in the `input_data/` folder.

At this point, the virtual environment is ready and the user can execute the demos. Inside the folder for each demo the user can find additional instructions for execution in a `README.txt`. Additionally, after launching the scripts a new folder, `/results`, is created. It contains the following subfolders:

- **figures:** Contains pictures used for the evaluation of the models.
- **logs:** Details with the logs of the execution.

- **models:** Stored models after the training is complete.

7 DEMOS

In this section we provide a categorized list of demos, organized by POM. In every one of the demo examples below, it is necessary to run every provided script line³ in a separate console.

7.1 POM1

7.1.1 Input data format verification

```
python pom1_check_data.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 1
```

7.1.2 Data conversion to numeric format

```
python pom1_data_to_numeric.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

7.1.3 Data alignment estimation

³ All the code (demos and libraries) is python 3, we use either “python” or “python3” in the scripts, but in all cases we are referring to execution under Python 3.

```
python poml_data_alignment_estimation.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24 --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24 --id 1  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24 --id 2
```

7.1.4 “Ad hoc” data pre-processing

```
python poml_adhoc_preprocess.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

7.1.5 Image reshape pre-processing

```
python poml_image_reshape_preprocessing.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 1
```

7.1.6 Data (global parameter) normalization

```
python poml_normalization.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task name
```

```
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

7.1.7 Dimensionality reduction

Principal Component Analysis (PCA):

```
python poml_principal_component_analysis.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

Greedy Feature Selection (GFS):

```
python poml_greedy_feature_selection.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

Feature Selection based on Frequency:

```
python poml_feature_selection_frequency.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 1
```

Random Projection:

```
python poml_random_projection.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse
```

```
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 1
```

7.1.8 Deep Learning Image Pre-processing

```
python poml_deep_learning_preprocessing.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 1
```

7.1.9 Natural Language Processing

```
python poml_natural_language_processing.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset 20news_bow_bin  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset 20news_bow_bin --id 0  
  
python poml_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset 20news_bow_bin --id 1
```

7.1.10 Record linkage in vertical partitioning

```
python poml_record_linkage.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw_V  
  
python poml_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V --id 0  
  
python poml_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V --id 1
```

7.1.11 Missing data imputation

```
python pom1_missing_data_imputation.py --user <user> --password <password>
--task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw_V_missing

python pom1_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V_missing --id 0

python pom1_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V_missing --id 1
```

7.1.12 Data value estimation

```
# A priori estimation

python pom1_data_value_estimation.py --user <user> --password <password> -
-task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist

python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 0

python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 1

python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 2

# A posteriori estimation

python pom1_data_value_estimation_pos.py --user <user> --password
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist

python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 0

python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 1

python pom1_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 2
```

7.2 POM2

7.2.1 Input data format verification

```
python pom2_check_data.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
```

```
<task_name> --dataset income_raw

python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0

python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 1
```

7.2.2 Data conversion to numeric format

```
python pom2_data_to_numeric.py --user <user> --password <password> --
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw

python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0

python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

7.2.3 Data alignment estimation

```
python pom2_data_alignment_estimation.py --user <user> --password
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24

python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24 --id 0

python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24 --id 1

python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24 --id 2
```

7.2.4 “Ad hoc” data pre-processing

```
python pom2_adhoc_preprocess.py --user <user> --password <password> --
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw

python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0

python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

7.2.5 Image reshape pre-processing

```
python pom2_image_reshape_preprocessing.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 1
```

7.2.6 Data (global parameter) normalization

```
python pom2_normalization.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

7.2.7 Dimensionality reduction

Principal Component Analysis (PCA):

```
python pom2_principal_component_analysis.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

Greedy Feature Selection (GFS):

```
python pom2_greedy_feature_selection.py --user <user> --password
```

```
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

Feature Selection based on Frequency:

```
python pom2_feature_selection_frequency.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 1
```

Random Projection:

```
python pom2_random_projection.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 1
```

7.2.8 Deep Learning Image Pre-processing

```
python pom2_deep_learning_preprocessing.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 1
```

7.2.9 Natural Language Processing

```
python pom2_natural_language_processing.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset 20news_bow_bin  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset 20news_bow_bin --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset 20news_bow_bin --id 1
```

7.2.10 Record linkage in vertical partitioning

```
python pom2_record_linkage.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw_V  
  
python pom2_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V --id 1
```

7.2.11 Missing data imputation

```
python pom2_missing_data_imputation.py --user <user> --password <password>  
--task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw_V_missing  
  
python pom2_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V_missing --id 0  
  
python pom2_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V_missing --id 1
```

7.2.12 Data value estimation

```
# A priori estimation  
  
python pom2_data_value_estimation.py --user <user> --password <password> -  
-task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 0
```

```
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 1  
  
python pom2_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 2
```

7.3 POM3

7.3.1 Input data format verification

```
python pom3_check_data.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 1
```

7.3.2 Data conversion to numeric format

```
python pom3_data_to_numeric.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

7.3.3 Data alignment estimation

```
python pom3_data_alignment_estimation.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24 --id 0  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24 --id 1  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
```

```
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_bad24 --id 2
```

7.3.4 “Ad hoc” data pre-processing

```
python pom3_adhoc_preprocess.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw
```

```
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0
```

```
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

7.3.5 Image reshape pre-processing

```
python pom3_image_reshape_preprocessing.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass
```

```
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 0
```

```
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 1
```

7.3.6 Data (global parameter) normalization

```
python pom3_normalization.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw
```

```
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0
```

```
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

7.3.7 Dimensionality reduction

Principal Component Analysis (PCA):

```
python pom3_principal_component_analysis.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

Greedy Feature Selection (GFS):

```
python pom3_greedy_feature_selection.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 0  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw --id 1
```

Feature Selection based on Frequency:

```
python pom3_feature_selection_frequency.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 0  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 1
```

Random Projection:

```
python pom3_random_projection.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 0
```

```
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset news20_all_sparse --id 1
```

7.3.8 Deep Learning Image Pre-processing

```
python pom3_deep_learning_preprocessing.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 0  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --id 1
```

7.3.9 Natural Language Processing

```
python pom3_natural_language_processing.py --user <user> --password  
<password> --task_name <task_name> --dataset 20news_bow_bin  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset 20news_bow_bin --id 0  
  
python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset 20news_bow_bin --id 1
```

7.3.10 Record linkage in vertical partitioning

```
python pom3_record_linkage.py --user <user> --password <password> --  
task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw_V  
  
python pom3_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V --id 0  
  
python pom3_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name  
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V --id 1
```

7.3.11 Missing data imputation

```
python pom3_missing_data_imputation.py --user <user> --password <password>
--task_name <task_name> --dataset income_raw_V_missing

python pom3_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V_missing --id 0

python pom3_worker_V.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset income_raw_V_missing --id 1
```

7.3.12 Data value estimation

```
# A priori estimation

python pom3_data_value_estimation.py --user <user> --password <password> -
-task_name <task_name> --dataset mnist

python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 0

python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 1

python pom3_worker.py --user <user> --password <password> --task_name
<task_name> --dataset mnist --id 2
```

7.4 POM4

7.4.1 Input data format verification

```
python3 pom4_check_data.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset redwine_raw --verbose 1 --id 0

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset redwine_raw --verbose 1 --id 2

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4

python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.2 Data conversion to numeric format

```
python3 pom4_data_to_numeric.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.3 Data alignment estimation

```
python3 pom4_data_alignment_estimation.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --
verbose 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 4
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.4 “Ad hoc” data pre-processing

```
python3 pom4_adhoc_preprocess.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

```
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.5 Image reshape pre-processing

```
python3 pom4_image_reshape_preprocessing.py --dataset  
mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --  
id 0  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --  
id 1  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --  
id 2  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --  
id 3  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --  
id 4  
  
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.6 Data (global parameter) normalization

```
python3 pom4_normalization.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4  
  
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.7 Dimensionality reduction

Principal Component Analysis (PCA):

```
python3 pom4_principal_component_analysis.py --dataset income_raw --  
verbose 1  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4  
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

Greedy Feature Selection (GFS):

```
python3 pom4_greedy_feature_selection.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4  
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

Feature Selection based on Frequency:

```
python3 pom4_feature_selection_frequency.py --dataset news20_all_sparse  
--verbose 1  
  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 0  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 1  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 2  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 3  
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 4  
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

Random Projection:

```
python3 pom4_random_projection.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 4
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.8 Deep Learning Image Pre-processing

```
python3 pom4_deep_learning_preprocessing.py --dataset
mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 0

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 1

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 2

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 3

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 4

python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.9 Natural Language Processing (TFIDF)

```
python3 pom4_natural_language_processing.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --
verbose 1

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 0
```

```
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 4
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.10 Record linkage in vertical partitioning

```
python3 pom4_record_linkage.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 4
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.11 Missing data imputation

```
python3 pom4_missing_data_imputation.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing
--verbose 1
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom4_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 4
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.4.12 Data value estimation

```
# A priori estimation

python3 pom4_data_value_estimation.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 4
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5

# A posteriori estimation

python3 pom4_data_value_estimation_pos.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1

python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom4_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 4
python3 pom4_crypto.py --verbose 1 --id 5
```

7.5 POM5

7.5.1 Input data format verification

```
python3 pom5_check_data.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset redwine_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset redwine_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
```

```
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.2 Data conversion to numeric format

```
python3 pom5_data_to_numeric.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.3 Data alignment estimation

```
python3 pom5_data_alignment_estimation.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --
verbose 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.4 “Ad hoc” data pre-processing

```
python3 pom5_adhoc_preprocess.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
```

```
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.5 Image reshape pre-processing

```
python3 pom5_image_reshape_preprocessing.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --id 0

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --id 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --id 2

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --id 3

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.6 Data (global parameter) normalization

```
python3 pom5_normalization.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.7 Dimensionality reduction

Principal Component Analysis (PCA):

```
python3 pom5_principal_component_analysis.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
```

```
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

Greedy Feature Selection (GFS):

```
python3 pom5_greedy_feature_selection.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

Feature Selection based on Frequency:

```
python3 pom5_feature_selection_frequency.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --
verbose 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 4
```

Random Projection:

```
python3 pom5_random_projection.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 1
```

```
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.8 Deep Learning Image Pre-processing

```
python3 pom5_deep_learning_preprocessing.py --dataset
mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 0

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 2

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 3

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 4
```

7.5.9 Natural Language Processing (TFIDF)

```
python3 pom5_natural_language_processing.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --
verbose 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 0

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 1

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 2

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 3

python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.10 Record linkage in vertical partitioning

```
python3 pom5_record_linkage.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.11 Missing data imputation

```
python3 pom5_missing_data_imputation.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --
verbose 1
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.5.12 Data value estimation

```
# A priori estimation
python3 pom5_data_value_estimation.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose
1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 4
# A posteriori estimation
python3 pom5_data_value_estimation_pos.py --dataset income_dv_small --
```

```
verbose 1  
  
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 0  
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 1  
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 2  
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 3  
python3 pom5_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6 POM6

7.6.1 Input data format verification

```
python3 pom6_check_data.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset redwine_raw --verbose 1 --id 0  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset redwine_raw --verbose 1 --id 2  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6.2 Data conversion to numeric format

```
python3 pom6_data_to_numeric.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3  
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6.3 Data alignment estimation

```
python3 pom6_data_alignment_estimation.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --
verbose 1

python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw_bad24 --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6.4 “Ad hoc” data pre-processing

```
python3 pom6_adhoc_preprocess.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6.5 Image reshape pre-processing

```
python3 pom6_image_reshape_preprocessing.py --dataset
mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1

python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
```

```
id 4
```

7.6.6 Data (global parameter) normalization

```
python3 pom6_normalization.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6.7 Dimensionality reduction

Principal Component Analysis (PCA):

```
python3 pom6_principal_component_analysis.py --dataset income_raw --
verbose 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

Greedy Feature Selection (GFS):

```
python3 pom6_greedy_feature_selection.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 2
```

```
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_raw --verbose 1 --id 4
```

Feature Selection based on Frequency:

```
python3 pom6_feature_selection_frequency.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --
verbose 1

python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 4
```

Random Projection:

```
python3 pom6_random_projection.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset news20_all_sparse --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6.8 Deep Learning Image Pre-processing

```
python3 pom6_deep_learning_preprocessing.py --dataset
mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1

python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 0

python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 1

python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
```

```
id 2

python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 3

python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset mnist_raw_matrix_binclass --verbose 1 --
id 4
```

7.6.9 Natural Language Processing (TFIDF)

```
python3 pom6_natural_language_processing.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --
verbose 1

python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset 20news_bow_bin --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6.10 Record linkage in vertical partitioning

```
python3 pom6_record_linkage.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6.11 Missing data imputation

```
python3 pom6_missing_data_imputation.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --
verbose 1
```

```
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker_V.py --dataset income_raw_V_missing --verbose 1 --id 4
```

7.6.12 Data value estimation

```
# A priori estimation
python3 pom6_data_value_estimation.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose
1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 4

# A posteriori estimation
python3 pom6_data_value_estimation_pos.py --dataset income_dv_small --
verbose 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 0
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 1
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 2
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 3
python3 pom6_worker.py --dataset income_dv_small --verbose 1 --id 4
```

8 Conclusions

In this deliverable (D4.3) we have presented the algorithms for data pre-processing, normalization, data alignment estimation and data value estimation

that have been incorporated into the MUSKETEER Machine Learning Library (MMLL). We have also included some demonstration scripts to illustrate their use under the different POMs. The methods currently available are used to carry out some operations on the distributed data before actually training a particular Machine Learning model and they will give support to the Data Scientist developing end user solutions in the MUSKETEER platform. We provide mechanisms that solve the following tasks: input data definition verification, data conversion to numeric format, "ad hoc" data pre-processing, data (global parameter) normalization, dimensionality reduction (Principal Component Analysis, Greedy Feature Selection, sparse frequency selection), random projection (full, sparse), deep Learning Image Pre-processing, Natural Language Processing, record linkage, missing data imputation, "a priori" data alignment estimation, and data value estimation ("a priori", "on-line" and "a posteriori").

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